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**To study the mycotic disease Saprolegniasis found in infected *Puntius sophore* fish
Pratap Kumar Sahu¹, Dr. Hemlata Nishad² and Dr. R.K. Singh¹**

¹Department of Zoology, Dr. C.V. Raman University, Kargi Road, Kota, Bilaspur
(C.G.) INDIA- 495113

² Department of Microbiology, Dr. C.V. Raman University, Kargi Road, Kota,
Bilaspur (C.G.) INDIA- 495113

Email: pratapkumarsahu83@gmail.com

Puntius sophore is one of the major food fish found in ponds of Mungeli District (Chhattisgarh). The infected *Puntius sophore* showed signs of saprolegniasis. In which the samples were taken between the month of July to November 2020. The length and weight of each sample were measured. The samples were taken separately in a polythene bag containing ice from a pond called Pathartal. These samples were kept in the Microbiology lab of CVRU Research center located at Dr.C.V. Raman University, Kargi Road Kota (Bilaspur) for in depth study and testing. Factors affecting infected *Puntius sophore Saprolegnia parasitica* studied. A culture medium called SDA(Sabouraud Dextrose Agar) was created to observe and identify the *Saprolegnia parasitica* fungus of infected *Puntius sophore*. Microscopic study was done to see the distinctive features of the fungus, for which methylene blue was used for staining. Photography of slide was taken by Dr. Rakesh Menghani (MD., Pathologist), Advanced Diagnostic Center, Tilak Nagar, Bilaspur (Chhattisgarh). Biochemical test of fungus presented in CVRU Research Center, Microbiology lab was done. MR (Methyl Red), VP (Voges Proskauer) and Indole (Kava's Indole) testing was done in biochemical test. As a result MR (Methyl Red) and Indole (Kava's Indole) test got positive (+ve) response while VP (Voges Proskauer) test got negative (-ve) response. *Saprolegnia parasitica* fungus confirmed. An experiment was carried out for control in which fresh *Puntius sophore* fish was taken, in which the above culture medium SDA (Sabouraud Dextrose Agar) was taken. During this time no colony of fungus was seen. Poor water quality, unsuitable temperature make it very easy to cause disease. Which causes an increase in the incidence of Saprolegniasis. Most of the outbreak of this disease is seen in the pond during the rainy season. This disease spreads very fast due to the arrival of contaminated water from outside in the pond.

Keywords-Puntius sophore fish, Saprolegniasis, Saprolegnia parasitica, culture medium SDA (Sabouraud Dextrose Agar), biochemical test and identification, microscopic observation.